

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN WORK MOTIVATION AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF AVIATION SECTOR EMPLOYEES

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Introduction

The aviation sector is a multinational market in which vigorous technology-based rivalry is revitalized. The world's economic and political problems, the promotions and resources of rivals, violence, and crime, and the instability situation have increased because of the latest pandemic (IATA, 2019).

In addition to the technological developments in the aviation sector, the need for trained personnel is a requirement that cannot be ignored. The job performances of the personnel in the sector, who provide services on a large scale starting from ground handling, cabin personnel and pilot, can be the biggest profit

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or loss of the companies. Business performance is very important in the aviation industry, as its operating leverage is high and profitability is very low (Grote, 2016).

This day, employees' performance is of great importance for businesses to achieve their goals and objectives and to gain competitive advantage (Begenirbaş & Turgut, 2014). Job performance is under the control of the individual and refers to the activities and behaviors that will contribute to the goals of the organization (Rotundo & Sackett, 2002). In general, job performance is important for the success of both employees and employers, as it refers to the behaviors of employees related to their organizational goals (Goldsmith & Johnson, 2002; Sony & Mekoth, 2016).

Organizations create up-to-date policies according to the requirements of the period. Organizations have a dynamic structure to continue their lives by showing continuous development and change. Both internal and external environment; It forces the organization and its human resources into an evolutionary-based transformation as a whole in the medium and long term. In this context, when both the whole organization and the individuals or groups within the organization tend to increase their performance level to a higher level, the said dynamic structure is positively affected. Otherwise, the livelihood of the organization is weakened. The concept that corporations focus heavily on in line with their policies is performance. The performance of the employees within the organization is determined by their personal characteristics and abilities, the desire to achieve their job, the ability of the management to activate this desire and the working environment provided. Job performance is not just an outcome depending on the employee. In addition to the employee's personal characteristics, skills, abilities and desire to succeed, the management's ability to mobilize this desire and the working environment together specify the job performance (Bükülmez, 2013).

Performance is a notion that is frequently used in the field of human resources management, but its boundaries and content are not sufficiently explained (Çalık, 2003). Organization managers have the responsibility of directing and evaluating the performance of subordinates as an officer of the organization.

Performance increase, which is the key to success in an organizational context, is not a product of a spontaneous process. In other words, performance should be perceived and managed as a strategic issue. Performance management is a systematic approach developed for human management for the use of performance, goals, criteria, feedback and recognition in the context of motivating the human resources in an organization to realize their maximum potential (Hume, 1998).

It is possible to talk about two basic dimensions of performance management in an organization. The first dimension is perceived organizational performance towards the integrity of the organization and the second dimension is individual performance (Barutçugil, 2002). In another approach, performance increase or decrease in an organization is a phenomenon that should be evaluated both in an organizational dimension and in an individual dimension.

Wage earners increase their motivation and performance levels when they believe it will result in a positive performance appraisal (organizational awards), but organizational awards are not the only factor affecting wage earner motivation and thus work performance. Besides organizational awards; there are numerous factors such as the nature of the job, working conditions, the use of skills, and the value given to people (Barutçugil, 2002).

In the aspect of organizations, motivation can be described as motivating wage earners and directing their wishes and behaviors in line with the goals that the business wants to achieve. In organizations, the concept of motivation can be expressed as "all efforts to continuously mobilize one or more people towards a certain goal" (Can, Büyükbacı, Bal & Ertemsir, 2013).

Motivation is; people acting with their own wishes and desires to achieve a specific goal (Koçel, 2003). According to another definition, motivation is the process of encouraging employees to work and making them believe that they will best satisfy their personal needs if they work efficiently in the organization. Motivation, which is perhaps the most important of human resources functions and directs human relations, is also the most neglected in practice.

Keeping the motivation of the managers high and not being able to predict what the company can gain is effective in this. Although some additional costs are required to keep motivation high, unfortunately the economic benefit cannot be directly measured. However, motivation aims to increase business efficiency on the one hand, and to increase the satisfaction that employees expect from the business on the other hand (Osterlah, Frey & Frost 2001). In addition, it is possible to attract more qualified personnel to the organization, to keep the existing qualified personnel within the organization for a long time, to have more efficient and high performance of employees, and to work environments where motivation is kept high (McNamara, 2003). It is possible to establish a relationship between performance and motivation. Maslow (1970) stated in his article “motivation and personality” that science cannot be independent from human values; It has revealed that meeting the needs of individuals in a hierarchical order (psychological, security, belonging, love and love, respect and self-realization) will direct individuals towards motivation. Again, Frederick Herzberg stated the importance of satisfaction and motivation level for performance increase in Two Factor Theory (Hume, 1998). The dissatisfaction that will arise at any level in an organization will decrease both motivation and performance, and create a conflict environment. Unmotivated personnel should not be expected to perform effectively and work efficiently. It is known that having a meaningful relationship between work motivation and work performance in working life increases quality production activities and productivity. For this reason, the work performance and job motivation of the aviation sector employees will be determined and analyzed in terms of some variables in the study.

The purpose of this study is to examine the job motivation and job performance of healthcare professionals in terms of some variables. In accordance with this purpose;

- 1- *Do the work motivations and job performances of aviation sector employees differ according to their gender?*
- 2- *What is the relationship between work motivation and the job performance of aviation sector employees? Answers to questions will be searched out.*

Method

The research was realized in a relational survey model in order to determine the relationship between work motivation and job performance of aviation industry employees. A relational survey model can be defined as “a research model that aims to determine the existence and/or degree of change between variables when there are two or more variables” (Karasar, 2005). The study universe of the research consists of aviation sector employees working in the airline transportation sector. The sample of the study, on the other hand, consists of a total of 300 aviation sector employees, 100 female (33%) and 200 male (67%), determined by random sampling method.

Scaling Tools:

1. Sociodemographic Data Form:

It includes a total of 5 questions about socio-demographic and occupational characteristics such as gender, age, education level, length of service at the institution, and professional experience.

2. Job Motivation Scale:

The scale is a 5-item Likert-type scale consisting of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation dimensions used by Mottaz (1985), Brislin, Kabigting, Macnab, Zukis, and Worthley (2005), Ertan (2008), Mahaney and Lederer (2006). Evaluation of work motivation scale 1.00-1.80 Very Low; 1.81-2.60 Low; 2.61-3.40 Medium; 3.41-4.20 High; 4.21-5.00 Very High. The work motivation of the employees is mainly determined by two types of tools: Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation tools. Among the intrinsic motivation tools, interesting and challenging work, independence at work, the importance of work for the employee, participation in the job, responsibility, diversity, creativity, opportunities to use one's abilities and skills, and satisfactory feedback factors about the person's performance are considered. Extrinsic motivation tools are addressed in two dimensions: First, social motivation tools, second, organizational tools. The first is based on the nature of interpersonal relationships such as friendship, benevolence, support of colleagues and the boss, while the second is related to the opportunities offered by

the organization to increase job performance, such as the adequacy of resources in the work environment, wage equality, promotion opportunity, additional benefits and job security (Mottaz, 1985. Dündar, Özutku & Taşpınar, 2007). The first 9 items in the work motivation scale are included in the intrinsic motivation dimension, and starting from the 10th item, all items including the 24th item are included in the extrinsic motivation dimension.

When Cronbach's Alpha Reliability results for this study are examined, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficients are .71 for intrinsic motivation, .80 for extrinsic motivation, and .78 for the whole scale.

3. Job Performance Scale:

In scaling the work performance of the employees; the job performance scale used first by Kirkman and Rosen (1999) and later by Sigler and Pearson (2000) was used. The reliability coefficient of the scale, which consists of four questions, is above .70 in both studies. Turkey Desert (2008) on the reliability coefficient applied by academics have been identified as .82. Answers in the study were taken with a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree). As a result of the confirmatory factor analysis, it was determined that the scale has a single factor structure, and its factor loads vary between .66 and .81. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was determined as .83. The KeizerMeyer-Olkin analysis result of the scale was .79 and the Barlett test was found to be significant ($p = .000$).

Findings

The distribution of some introductory characteristics such as gender, age, education level, working time and professional experience of the aviation sector employees participating in the study is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Frequency and percentage distribution regarding the demographic characteristics of Aviation Sector employees

Variations	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
Gender	Male	200	67
	Female	100	33
Age	20-30 Years old	130	43
	31-40 Years old	70	24
	41 and over	100	33
Education Level	Primary School	100	33
	High School	90	30
	Bachelor	110	37
Working Duration in the Same Institution	1-10 Years	115	39
	11-20 Years	85	28
	21 Years and over	100	33
Professional Experience	1-10 Years	92	30,5
	11-20 Years	76	25,2
	21 Years and over	134	44,4

When the participants in the study are examined in terms of their demographic characteristics; it is seen that 67% of the sample consisting of 300 people participating in the research is male and 33% is female. Looking at the age distribution, it is seen that 43% of the majority are in the 20-30 age range, 24% in the 31-40 age range and 33% in the age range 41 and above. Considering the distribution for educational status; 33% of primary education, 30% of high school and 37% of them have received education at the undergraduate level. The distribution of the research participants according to the duration of their employment in the same institution is seen that 39% worked in the same institution for 1-10 years, 28% for 11-20 years and 33% for over 21 years. In the distribution of occupational experience that expresses the duration of the participants' work in the aviation sector, 30.5% of the sample, those who work for less than 10 years, 25.2% who work between 11 and 20 years, 44.4% of those who work 21 years or more.

Data on the work motivation levels of aviation sector employees according to their gender are given in Table 2.

Table 2. The t-test results of the work motivation scale sub-dimensions related to the gender of aviation sector employees

Dimensions	Gender	N	X	Ss	t	p
Team	Male	200	15,72	4,63	-3,142	,002
Adaptation	Female	100	17,16	3,52		
Business	Male	200	16,64	3,80	-1,622	,090
Integration	Female	100	15,87	3,72		
Commitment to the Institution	Male	200	12,31	3,28	-3,714	,001
	Female	100	12,18	2,66		
Personal Development	Male	200	12,22	3,17	-1,221	,147
	Female	100	12,51	3,26		

*p<.05

When the sub-dimensions of the Work Motivation Scale of aviation sector employees were examined by gender, the arithmetic mean of male employees ($X = 15.72$) and the arithmetic mean of female employees ($X = 17.16$) were found in the sub-dimension of team harmony. A significant difference was found between the averages ($t = -3.142$ $p > .05$). The level of team cohesion in the work motivation of female employees was found to be higher than that of male employees. When the job integration sub-dimension was examined, the arithmetic mean of male employees ($X = 16.64$) and the arithmetic mean of female employees were found ($X = 15.87$). There was no significant difference found between the averages ($t = -1.622$ $p > .05$). When the sub-dimension of commitment to the organization was examined, the arithmetic mean of male employees ($X = 12.31$) and the arithmetic mean of female employees ($X = 12.18$) were found. There was a significant difference found between the averages ($t = -3.714$ $p > .05$). The level of commitment to the institution in the work motivation of female employees was found to be higher than that of male employees. When the personal development sub-dimension was examined, the arithmetic mean of male employees ($X = 12.22$)

and the arithmetic mean of female employees ($X = 12.51$) were found. No significant difference was found between the averages ($t = -1,221$ $p > .05$). Data on job performance levels of aviation sector employees according to their gender is given in Table 3.

Table 3. T Test results of the sub-dimensions of the job performance scale regarding the gender of aviation sector employees

Dimensions	Gende		X	Ss	t	p
	r	N				
Mission Performance	Male	200	43,16	15,51	-4,132	,001
	Female	100	39,30	13,84		
Contextual Performance	Male	200	28,12	9,37	,295	,187
	Female	100	26,25	9,22		

* $p < .05$

When the sub-dimensions of the Job Performance Scale of aviation sector employees were examined by gender when the task performance sub-dimension was examined, the arithmetic mean of male employees ($X = 43,16$) and the arithmetic mean of female employees ($X = 39,30$) were found. A significant difference was found between the averages ($t = -4.132$ $p > .05$). The level of task performance of female employees in job performance was found to be higher than that of male employees. When the contextual performance sub-dimension was examined, the arithmetic mean of male employees ($X = 28.12$) and the arithmetic mean of female employees ($X = 26.25$) were found.

There was no significant difference between the averages ($t = ,295$ $p > .05$). Data on the relationship between work motivation and job performance of aviation industry employees are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Correlation values of the relationship between work motivation and job performance of aviation sector employees

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Team Adaptation	-					
2. Business Integration	.488**	-				
3. Commitment to the Institution	.395**	.387**	-			
4. Personal Development	.421**	.510**	.365**	-		
5. Mission Performance	.397**	.504**	.711**	.621**	-	
6. Contextual Performance	.401**	.502**	.612**	.502**	.512**	-

When Table 4 is examined, between the team adaptation sub-dimension of the Work Motivation Scale and the integration with work sub-dimension, $r = .488$ ($p < .01$), between the corporate commitment sub-dimension and $r = .395$ ($p < .01$), the personal development sub-dimension A positive correlation was found between $r = .421$ ($p < .01$), task performance sub-dimension forward = $.397$ ($p < .01$) and contextual performance at the level of $r = .401$ ($p < .01$). Work integration sub-dimension and commitment to the organization sub-dimension $r = .387$ ($p < .01$), between personal development sub-dimension $r = .510$ ($p < .01$), task performance sub-dimension and $r = .504$ ($p < .01$)) and contextual performance at the level of $r = .502$ ($p < .01$). Between the commitment to the institution sub-dimension and the personal development sub-dimension, $r = .365$ ($p < .01$), between the task performance sub-dimension and $r = .711$ ($p < .01$), and between contextual performance, $r = .612$ ($p < .01$) A positive relationship was found at the level. A positive relationship was found between personal development and task performance sub-dimension and $r = .621$ ($p < .01$) and contextual performance at the level of $r = .502$ ($p < .01$). A positive relationship was found between task performance and contextual performance at the level of $r = .512$ ($p < .01$).

Discussion

Is there a significant difference in the work motivation of aviation sector employees according to the gender variable? Examining the results of the question, the loyalty and devotion of the female staff to the company was found to be greater than that of the male employees.

Taşpınar (2008) and Smith (1999) indicated in their studies that gender has no effect on motivation level. The related literature does not support these findings. When the findings of the second sub-problem of the study, "Is there a significant difference in work motivation of aviation sector employees according to the age variable?" It was found to be higher than that.

As a result of their research, Baysal and Paksoy (1999) found a meaningful and positive relationship between the age variable and continuing the profession, emotional commitment to the organization, and continuing in the organization. When the relevant literature is examined, it is in line with this finding of the study.

When the findings of the other sub-problem of the study, "Is there a significant difference in work motivation according to the education level variable of aviation sector employees? ", It was found that industrial employees who received education at primary education level had higher job integration and personal development levels compared to those who received high school and undergraduate education.

When the findings of the study related to the question "Is there a significant difference in the work motivation of aviation sector employees according to the professional experience variable? ", It was determined that those with 1-10 years of professional experience were high in team harmony, work integration, commitment to the institution and personal development.

Taşpınar (2006) pointed that workers who work for less than 1 year in a workplace have higher working motivation than other groups. The findings of the study are in line with the literature. In a study conducted to determine the

relationship between the age and performance of employees, it was observed that while young employees produce the highest amount of work, older workers produce higher quality work (Iun & Huang, 2007). causes.

When the findings of the study regarding the question "Is there a significant relationship between the work motivation of aviation sector employees and their job performance?", It was found that there is a positive and significant relationship between job motivation and all its sub-dimensions and work performance sub-dimensions.

Support for colleagues is much more critical in working environments with collaboration and diversity of employees. The collaboration is more influential on the part of colleagues. It may also be seen that certain work performance-related habits are influenced by their coworkers. This influence is said to improve employment efficiency (Bateman, 2009).

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XÜLASƏ

Aviasiya Sektoru İşçilərinin İş Motivasiyası ilə İş icraları arasındakı əlaqə

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Milli iqtisadiyyatın həyati bir hissəsi xidmət sektoruna daxil olan aviasiya sektorudur. Aviasiya işçilərinin iş həvəsi və uğuru şirkət hədəflərinin yerinə yetirilməsinə öz təsirini göstərir. Xüsusilə aviasiya sektorunda "insan" məhsulunun keyfiyyəti böyük ölçüdə təyin edilir. İşçilərin iş motivasiyası, sevimli və uğurlu işləri təşkilatın fəaliyyətini böyük dərəcədə müəyyənləşdirəcəkdir. Buna görə də rəqabətdə üstünlük qazanmaq istəyən təşkilatlar işçilərinin motivasiyasına və iş icraslarına xüsusi diqqət yetirməlidirlər.

Bu məqalədə də aviasiya sənayesi işçilərinin iş motivasiyası, iş icra səviyyələri və onlar arasındakı əlaqələr araşdırılmışdır.

Açar sözlər: Aviasiya sektoru, aviasiya işçisi, iş motivasiyası , iş icrası

РЕЗЮМЕ

Взаимосвязь между трудовой мотивации и эффективности работы сотрудников авиационного сектора

Седа БАХАДИР ДУРСАН
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Жизненно важной частью национальной экономики является авиационный сектор, который входит в сферу обслуживания. Энтузиазм к работе и успех работы авиастроителей влияют на достижение целей компании. В частности, в авиационном секторе «человек» в значительной степени определяет качество продукта. Трудовая мотивация сотрудников, их любящая и успешная работа во многом определяют эффективность работы организации. Поэтому организации, которые хотят получить конкурентное преимущество, должны уделять особое внимание мотивации и производительности своих сотрудников.

В данной статье исследуются трудовая мотивация и уровень производительности сотрудников авиационной отрасли, а также взаимоотношения между ними.

Ключевые слова: Авиационный сектор, авиационный персонал, трудовая мотивация, эффективность работы

ELM VƏ İNNOVATİV
TEKNOLOGİYALAR
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